

STEAMed SPNHC Manual

How to STEAM SPNHC

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Last Updated: June 2025 | **Template Materials & Forms:** [Templates](#)

Zenodo: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15610303 | **Google Doc:** [STEAMed SPNHC Manual](#)

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Introduction

Purpose of the Manual

This manual serves as a living guide to organizing and sustaining the STEAMed SPNHC initiative—an effort to integrate art into the [SPNHC \(Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections\)](#) conference. It is designed to support both new and returning organizers, providing structure, inspiration, and practical tools for planning and executing the initiative’s core activities: the Silent Art Auction, the Artist’s Corner, and an Unconference.

Vision of STEAMed SPNHC

STEAMed SPNHC explores the intersection of art and science to foster creativity, collaboration, and deeper engagement within the natural history collections community. By integrating artistic perspectives into the conference, it offers new ways to address challenges in scientific communication, inclusion, and sustainability, while creating intentional dynamic spaces for dialogue and innovation. Through events like the Silent Art Auction, Artist’s Corner, and Unconference, STEAMed SPNHC highlights the creative talents within and beyond our field, invites cross-disciplinary collaborations and partnerships, and reimagines how collections can extend and expand their relevance and responsiveness to both local and global needs.

Concept Note:

The ideas for this series of events come from author Deborah Paul. The gestalt for these related events is based on her assertions that the arts and artists (and other disciplines like engineering, architecture, fashion design, economics, etc) can help us be strategic in our effort to:

- strengthen the recognition of collections and collections expertise in local communities and hence their potential inclusion, relevance, and connections to local projects, organizations, people, and departments. This provides a key opportunity in managing the risk we note where we are often “talking to ourselves.” We need to make concrete efforts to invite other domains into our world.
- address the perception of “elitism” and the need for expertise that opens doors
- make an intentional space to help others find their agency and relevance with “our” world
- engage with many audiences add their voices in conveying the importance and value of what we do
- reframe “us” and “them” conversations to “us” as connected and all inhabitants of the same planet
- find our storytellers and collaborators helping us to start and sustain these conversations

Overview of Key Activities

The STEAMed SPNHC program currently consists of three primary components. Each is designed to engage different audiences and types of participation, and each can be adapted over time to fit the needs, resources, and opportunities.

Silent Art Auction

The [Silent Art Auction](#) invites local host institutions/departments/businesses and SPNHC members and affiliated domains, local artists, and affiliated creatives to donate items—ranging from scientific illustration and handmade objects to repurposed field gear, prints, and books—for a community auction. Proceeds directly support the **SPNHC Student Travel Fund**. The auction generates visibility for artists and collections-based creativity while creating a meaningful and fun way to support early-career participation in the society.

Artist's Corner

The [Artist's Corner](#) is a flexible, informal space, and an intentional space, where artists and anyone within and beyond the SPNHC community can gather to create, share their work, and engage directly with attendees. Whether through live demonstrations, material displays, informal conversations on any topic, or simply making art in real time, this space invites reflection, connection, and creativity. It highlights the role of artists as collaborators in collections work—not as outsiders, but as integral members of our community whose practices enrich how we communicate, interpret, and imagine science. It is an “intentional” water cooler space.

Unconference

The [Unconference](#) is a participant-driven session designed to explore the integration and potential of art and science within natural history work. Unlike traditional panels or symposia, this format invites attendees to pitch new or hot topics, form breakout groups, and engage in collaborative discussions on themes such as science communication through art, models of interdisciplinary partnership, and the motivations behind art-science collaboration. The open structure encourages dynamic, creative exchange and fosters actionable timely ideas. Participants leave with new connections, fresh perspectives, and practical resources.

Getting Started

The first step in organizing STEAMed SPNHC programming is to establish a clear point of contact with the Local Organizing Committee (LOC). This individual (or team) will be essential for coordinating logistics, securing space, aligning outreach with broader conference communications, and ensuring activities are integrated smoothly into the overall program. Work

with them early to determine general timing and location. In most cases, the Silent Art Auction should open shortly after the conference's plenary or opening remarks (see [Week-of Logistics](#)) and remain available throughout the week, with item pickup scheduled for the final full day. The Artist's Corner typically shares space with the auction, so its setup and availability should be coordinated in parallel (see [Space Setup](#)). The Unconference session, while more self-contained, still requires inclusion in the official schedule and an appropriate location, ideally one with flexible seating and breakout space (see [Space and Setup](#)). Locating these spaces near the exhibitor / vendor space also ensures discovery of and facilitates engagement in the STEAMed SPNHC activities.

Organizers are typically required to submit an abstract or session proposal to the official conference platform in order for STEAMed SPNHC events to appear in the printed or digital program. This submission provides visibility to attendees and lends legitimacy to events like the auction, Artist's Corner, and Unconference.

[Template abstracts can be accessed here:](#)

[Abstract Templates](#)

Additionally, it is recommended to request a dedicated page on the conference website to serve as a centralized landing space for information. This page can be referenced in emails, advertisements, and social media announcements.

Silent Art Auction

Planning Timeline

Planning the Silent Art Auction should begin several months before the conference to allow for sufficient coordination, outreach, and logistics. Ideally, organizers will start by confirming the auction's inclusion with the LOC and securing space and general scheduling within the conference program. From there, efforts should proceed in roughly three overlapping phases: **early planning and outreach, donation and volunteer coordination, and final logistics and execution.**

Early Planning (3–6 months out)

Secure LOC approval, determine auction space needs, and finalize guidelines for what types of items will be accepted (See [Starting Out](#)). Begin recruiting volunteers and outreach to SPNHC members, local artists, and institutions (See [Recruiting and Managing Volunteers](#)). Launch the donation form and begin advertising the call for contributions across SPNHC communication channels (See [Donation Process](#)). This is also the time to submit any required abstract or session description for inclusion in the conference program.

Mid-Stage Coordination (2–3 months out)

Actively track donations and responses using a shared spreadsheet (See [Donation Tracking Sheet](#)). Organize submissions by item and confirm delivery method (e.g., shipping or in-person drop-off). Maintain communication with donors, especially regarding fragile or high-value items. Begin developing promotional materials and share previews of donated items with donor permission (See [Advertising and Outreach](#)). Recruit and begin scheduling volunteers based on preliminary conference timing.

Final Preparations and Conference Week (1 month out – onsite)

Send detailed logistics emails to both donors and volunteers, confirming delivery details, responsibilities, and schedules. Reach back out to anyone who previously expressed interest in donating but didn't complete the form—these follow-ups often yield last-minute contributions (See [Recruiting and Managing Volunteers](#)). Finalize and print bid sheets, signage, and any promotional materials. Begin gathering materials for the auction table itself. Coordinate closely with the LOC on setup needs and confirm QR codes or payment logistics with the SPNHC Treasurer (See [Payment](#)). Set up the auction space at the start of the conference, monitor the space throughout the week, and close bidding on the penultimate day (See [Week-of Logistics](#)). Process payments and item pickups on the final day, ensuring that any unclaimed items are handled according to donor instructions or follow-up efforts.

Donation Process

The success of the Silent Art Auction depends on the generosity, creativity, and enthusiasm of our community. Donations can come from SPNHC members, other related community organization members (like folks from Botany, or the American Society of Mammalogists), local artists, museums, and vendors.

Item Criteria

The auction welcomes a wide range of donations, with an intentionally broad and inclusive definition of “art.” Donors are encouraged to interpret this on their own terms—whether through original artwork, handmade crafts, collection-inspired objects, tools, books, or field equipment. Items do not need to be themed around natural history or tied to a donor’s institutional affiliation. While many submissions do naturally reflect SPNHC’s collections-focused mission, all are welcome.

At present, there is no formal vetting process for submitted items beyond reviewing item descriptions as they come in. That said, the auction is not intended as a place for reprints, outdated handouts, broken equipment, or miscellaneous collection overflow. Specimens are also discouraged. Should issues arise in the future regarding the appropriateness or quality of donations, the organizers may develop more detailed submission guidelines and a formal review process to maintain the integrity and spirit of the event.

Shipping Items

Donors who are unable to hand-deliver their contributions may choose to ship items ahead of the conference. Organizers should coordinate with the LOC to confirm a secure shipping address and identify someone responsible for receiving, storing, and transporting items to the auction site. Organizers should reach out to donors wishing to ship their items at least a month before the conference.

Because of the logistical burden, **shipping post-conference is discouraged** unless absolutely necessary. Donors must indicate on the submission form what they would like done with their item(s) if they do not sell. Options include retrieving the item in person during the designated pickup period or donating it back to SPNHC for future auctions or potential gifting to an appropriate institution or initiative.

Minimum Bids

All items submitted to the Silent Art Auction **must include a minimum bid**, which must be set by the donor at the time of submission via the donation form. The minimum bid will be displayed on the corresponding bid sheet.

Donation Form

All donors must complete a **Silent Art Auction Donation Form** to register their contributions. This information is used to generate bid sheets, organize the auction display, and guide

pre-conference promotion. The live responses automatically populate a spreadsheet used by organizers to catalog incoming donations and plan logistics. The form is structured to allow multiple related items to be submitted in a single entry, though some donors may prefer to submit separate forms for individual items—both approaches are acceptable.

The form also allows donors to upload images of their items. These images are automatically stored in a connected folder linked to the response spreadsheet. Photos may be used for promotional purposes if permission is given—such as social media posts or email spotlights—and, if needed, informally vetting submissions.

[A template form, its responses and image folder can be accessed here:](#)

 [Donations Form Template](#)

The form collects the following details:

- **Name and Email:** For follow-up and confirmation.
- **Type of Item(s):** A short label (e.g., "prints," "pottery," "mixed media").
- **Item Description:** A brief description for the bid sheet—include material, theme, or story behind the piece.
- **Quantity of Items:** Helps organizers plan table space and labeling.
- **Minimum Bid:** Donors must choose to set starting bids for their items. For each item, they'll be asked to:
 - Identify the item,
 - Upload a photo (optional but encouraged), and
 - Specify the minimum bid amount.

This allows flexibility for donors who may be contributing multiple unique items under a single type.
- **Delivery Method:** Donors indicate whether they will **bring items in person** or **ship them ahead of time**. Organizers should follow up with shippers to confirm logistics and deadlines.
- **Special Handling Needs:** For example, if an item is fragile, needs to be hung, includes lighting, or requires a display stand. This informs both setup and volunteer support.
- **Post-Auction Preferences:** Donors specify what they'd like done with items that do not sell. **Note:** Items will not be shipped back after the conference; donors must reclaim them in person or agree to donate them to future auctions.
- **Promotional Consent:** Donors can opt in to being featured in social media posts or promotional materials.

- **Credit Preferences:** Donors choose how they would like their name (or group name) to appear on the bid sheet. Anonymity is also an option.
- **Additional Notes:** Open space for donors to include context, notes on donations exceeding form capacity, or special requests.
- **Image Upload:** An optional final upload for a group photo of all donated items or distinguishing photos of items not covered earlier.

Donation Tracking Sheet

Submissions are automatically compiled in a **Donation Form Response Spreadsheet**. Organizers will need to restructure the response data so that each individual donation becomes its own line item. While the original form response sheet allows for multiple items in a single entry, converting the data into a one-item-per-row format allows it to serve as a more functional working catalog. This working sheet must be **kept as up to date as possible** throughout the conference. Some donors may bring items the day of the auction that were never formally registered, while others may submit forms but ultimately not follow through. In addition, some donations may be split into smaller lots (e.g., a set of note cards divided into pairs) or grouped together (e.g., multiple small items forming a bundle)—these changes should be clearly reflected in the spreadsheet to avoid confusion during setup, bidding, and pickup.

[A template donation tracking sheet can be accessed here:](#)

 [Donation Tracking Sheet Template](#)

Bid Sheets

Bid sheets are used to display item information and collect in-person written bids during the Silent Art Auction. Each item should have its own sheet that includes the item number, description, donor credit, and the donor-specified minimum bid. Attendees write their name, email and bid amount directly on the sheet, and the highest valid bid at the close of the auction determines the winner.

Bid sheets can be efficiently generated using Microsoft Word's Mail Merge feature. This tool enables you to design a single bid sheet template and automatically populate it with item-specific information by connecting it to a spreadsheet, here the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#). Each row in the spreadsheet represents a separate item, and Mail Merge creates a formatted bid sheet for each one using the corresponding details. Below is a basic tutorial on how to set this up.

Mail Merge

Start with a template or blank document in Word, then go to **Mailings > Start Mail Merge > Step-by-step Mail Merge Wizard**.

1. In Step 1, choose **Letters**.
2. In Step 2, select **Use the current document**.
3. In Step 3, click **Browse** under “Use an existing list” and select the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#) (Excel file). Choose the correct worksheet and check the rows you want to include.
4. In Step 4, add merge fields to your template by selecting **More Items...**, then insert the fields (e.g., <<Donor>>, <<Item Description>>) where needed.
5. In Step 5, preview the documents using the arrow buttons—don’t make edits here.
6. In Step 6, click **Edit Individual Letters** to generate a new document with one completed bid sheet per item. You can now review, edit, and print as usual.

For future events, we recommend exploring a digital auction platform to complement or replace the physical bid sheets. This could allow attendees to browse items online, place bids remotely, and receive real-time updates on bidding activity.

A template bid sheet can be accessed here:

[W Bid Sheet Template](#)

Payment

The Silent Art Auction accepts several forms of payment, including **PayPal**, **Stripe** (for credit cards), **cash**, and **checks**. SPNHC’s Treasurer (treasurer@spnhc.org) can provide QR codes for both PayPal and Stripe, which can be printed and posted at the auction payment station. All payment methods should be tracked by item in the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#).

Digital payments are the preferred method. Attendees can scan the provided QR codes to complete transactions via PayPal (which requires the app) or Stripe (which is accessible for non-USA attendees). These payments are deposited directly into SPNHC’s accounts.

Cash and checks may also be accepted on-site, but require additional responsibility from the organizers. In these cases, the person collecting payment must submit the equivalent amount using one of the digital payment methods and keep the physical funds.

Note: To simplify payment processing, all bids must be in whole dollar amounts. Minimum bid increments should be set at one dollar.

After the conference, auction organizers must compile a **final payment report** for the Treasurer. This report should include:

- **Item number**
- **Winner name (Often, if winners have more than one item to pay for, they will combine the total amount into one transaction)**
- **Final sale price**

- **Payment method used (PayPal, Stripe, cash, or check)**

A report template can be accessed here:

 [Payment Report Template](#)

In addition, all **letters of receipt** issued for tax-deductible donations should be shared with the Treasurer for SPNHC's records. Similar to the bid sheets, letters can be generated through Word's [Mail Merge](#) function, using the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#) as the database.

A template letter of receipt can be accessed here:

 [Letter of Receipt Template](#)

Week-of Logistics

Announcements and Visibility

Ask conference organizers to **announce the auction's opening and closing times during the opening remarks and again just before bidding closes**. These messages can be supported by a PowerPoint slide that is shown before or between sessions. Extra announcements can also be made in relevant sessions, poster hours, or exhibit hall gatherings. These announcements also help encourage bidding.

Clear signage with opening and closing times should also be placed:

- At the auction area
- At the organizer desk
- At the registration desk

Auction Setup and Layout

The Silent Art Auction should ideally be set up in a high-traffic area, such as near the exhibit hall, poster space, or refreshment tables to ensure visibility and engagement.

Use the following display guidelines:

- Plan for a maximum of 10 items per 6-foot table, depending on item size and layout
- Use both sides of the table
- Use stands for books, framed art, and prints
- Use easels for large or oversized works
- Bring pens and **extra empty bid sheets (~30)**
- Refer to the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#) to identify items that require special handling or display instructions

A dedicated table and chairs for auction organizers should be included in the setup. This serves as a help station, item drop-off and pick-up area, and payment desk. It should be well-signed and easily visible from the main auction display.

Drop-Off and Pick-Up Procedures

The organizer and registration desks can also function as the official drop-off and pick-up location for auction items. Make sure the volunteers running the registration desk are aware so they can guide folks dropping off art. At the Silent Art Auction desk, volunteers will:

- Verify donation details
- Match the item to its entry in the tracking sheet and mark it off
- Ensure it is labeled and placed appropriately

After the auction closes, item pick-up should be scheduled for the final full day of the conference. Winners will collect their items at the organizer desk after showing payment confirmation. Volunteers should:

- Collect the winning bid sheet
- Receive [payment](#)
- Mark in the [Donation Tracking Sheet](#) what payment method was used and that the item has been picked up
- Mark as paid on the bid sheet

It can be very helpful to provide **packing materials** for fragile items at the pickup station. Many donors leave behind protective materials, such as boxes, bubble wrap, or padding, when dropping off their items, and these can often be reused by winning bidders. However, to ensure all needs are covered, organizers should still plan to have a small supply of extra materials on hand, including cardboard, tape, and bubble wrap.

Unclaimed items should first be followed up with additional outreach to the winning bidder through email and announcements. If the original winner fails to respond or pick up the item within a reasonable timeframe, organizers should attempt to offer the item to the second-highest bidder at their final bid amount. Only if these efforts are unsuccessful should the item be handled according to the donor's stated preferences on the donation form—redonating it to SPNHC for a future event or returning it to the donor if they are still onsite.

Auction Timing

- **Auction set-up and drop off happens the day prior and morning before the plenary**, typically while the registration desk is open
- **Auction opens shortly after the opening plenary**, allowing attendees to browse and bid throughout the week.
- **Bidding closes on the second-to-last full day of programming**, often at the end of sessions or during the final poster block.

- **Item pickup and payment take place on the final full day** of the conference

Attendees have occasionally gathered near the auction in the final minutes to place last-second bids and immediately collect the item for payment. While technically allowed, this practice can undermine the spirit of the event and make it more difficult for others to participate fairly. Moving to a digital bidding platform in the future would allow for implementation of extensions to bids, disallowing bid sniping.

Notifying Winners and Donors

Once the auction closes:

1. Volunteers should collect bid sheets and identify the winning bids
2. The winning bidder list should be:
 - **Emailed to winners** using the contact information provided on the bid sheet
 - **Printed and posted** in the auction space and around the conference space where useful

Final reminders should be made on the pick-up day, alerting attendees that:

- The printed list of winning bids is posted
- Item pick-up is happening and will close at end of day

This helps ensure that winners know they've won and remember to retrieve and pay for their items before the conference ends. It is equally important to alert donors whose items did not sell that they need to pick up their unsold contributions before the conference concludes, as no post-conference shipping will be provided unless previously arranged.

Artist's Corner

Overview and Purpose

The Artist's Corner is a flexible, informal space designed to foster creativity, dialogue, and reflection. Open to anyone interested in exploring the intersection of art and natural history, it invites both artists and non-artists to create, observe, and engage. While the space is open to all SPNHC attendees, featured contributors may include local invited artists who are encouraged to share their work, lead informal demonstrations, and engage directly with the collections community.

The Corner serves multiple purposes: it highlights the creative work already present within the collections world; it provides a low-pressure, welcoming environment for spontaneous artistic activity; and it offers attendees a moment to rest, reflect, and connect through shared creative practice. Whether contributing artwork, sitting down to sketch, or simply observing, participants are encouraged to engage with art as a meaningful way to explore sustainability, communication, and collaboration in natural history. It is very literally meant as an intentional “water cooler.”

Planning Timeline

Planning the Artist's Corner should begin several months before the conference to ensure meaningful participation, thoughtful setup, and smooth coordination with other STEAMed SPNHC activities. Ideally, organizers will first confirm space and general timing with the LOC. From there, planning can move through three overlapping phases: **early visioning and outreach, artist and volunteer coordination, and final logistics and onsite support.**

Early Planning (3–5 months out)

Secure LOC approval. Be sure there is adequate space for the Artist's Corner, ideally near or co-located with the Silent Auction (see [Space Setup and Co-Location](#)). This includes submitting any necessary abstracts or descriptions (see [Getting Started](#)). Identify a general format or tone for the space: whether there will be live demos, drop-in activities, reflective art spaces, or informal talks (see [Activities and Programming](#)). Begin outreach to potential contributors, including local creatives, and museum or university art faculty or other interested departments / organizations (e.g. engineering, humanities, architecture, design, etc). A call for participation can be included in the same outreach materials used for recruiting volunteers (see [Recruiting and Managing Volunteers](#) and [Artist Outreach and Recruitment](#)).

Mid-Stage Coordination (2–3 months out)

Actively recruit and confirm participating artists. Ask them for bios, availability, supply needs, and whether they're willing to be featured in conference promotional materials. Begin scheduling

activities and determining how the space will be used across different days. Encourage artists to bring their own materials and displays but consider providing shared art supplies for drop-in or reflective activities (e.g., markers, paper, craft supplies).

Begin assigning volunteer shifts and gathering names of helpers who can assist with setup, staffing, and light facilitation (see [Recruiting and Managing Volunteers](#)). Draft promotional materials for use in SPNHC newsletters, Slack, and social media. If artists submit photos of their work or proposed activities, these can be featured in teaser content, with their permission.

Final Preparations and Conference Week (1 month out – onsite)

Send final confirmation emails to artists and volunteers with details on space location, setup times, and expectations. Check with the LOC to ensure all materials and furniture will be available onsite. Confirm the final schedule of participation and display it at the conference site and online, if possible.

Onsite, set up the Artist's Corner at the beginning of the conference. Ensure shared supplies are stocked and accessible. Volunteers can help keep the space tidy, answer questions, and support artists as needed.

Artist Outreach and Recruitment

Recruitment for the Artist's Corner can be incorporated into general volunteer outreach efforts (See [Recruiting and Managing Volunteers](#)). In addition to seeking help with setup, staffing, or facilitation, organizers should specifically invite individuals interested in contributing creative work or leading art-based activities. Volunteers who want to showcase their own artwork, contribute materials, or donate time to interactive elements, such as demonstrations or open studio sessions, are especially valuable.

Potential participants may include:

- SPNHC members who identify as artists
- Local or regional artists with an interest in science, nature, or sustainability
- Art students or faculty from nearby colleges and universities
- Artists affiliated with the host institution or local museums

Outreach can be conducted through SPNHC Slack, NHCOLL-L, local arts organizations, or by reaching out directly to potential contributors. When inviting artists, be clear about what participation might look like—e.g., providing a demo, displaying work, offering an informal Q&A—and confirm whether they'd like to be featured in promotional materials.

Activities and Programming

The Artist's Corner is designed to be an open, welcoming environment where creativity and community can flourish side-by-side. It supports a wide variety of informal, participatory experiences that invite engagement at any level. Conversations are expected to emerge naturally as artists and attendees work side-by-side.

- **Live Art-Making or Demonstrations:** Artists creating work in real time invite curiosity and spark spontaneous dialogue. These moments transform passive observation into active engagement, offering insight into artistic processes and technique while building connection with the audience.
- **Drop-In Projects:** Casual, self-guided activities such as creative journaling, collaborative sketchbooks, sticker design, or collective mural boards encourage hands-on participation. These are especially effective for attendees who may not identify as artists but want to engage creatively.
- **Displays of Sketchbooks and Process Work:** Contributors can showcase in-progress pieces, field sketchbooks, or annotated prints to highlight the behind-the-scenes thinking and experimentation shared by both scientific and artistic practices.
- **Quiet, Reflective Creative Space:** Offering materials like coloring sheets, watercolor sets, origami paper, or collage supplies can provide attendees a restful break from the busy conference atmosphere. These spaces promote mindfulness and a low-pressure form of creative exploration.

The Artist's Corner doesn't require rigid scheduling to be effective. Its strength lies in its flexibility, openness, and its ability to generate authentic moments of connection between people, practice, and purpose.

Space Setup

Space needs should be coordinated with the LOC well in advance to determine location, layout, and any equipment or infrastructure needs.

Core setup might include:

- **Tables and chairs** for artists and attendees to work, rest, or converse
- **Easels or display stands** for showing works-in-progress, prints, or demo pieces
- **Signage** including artist bios, descriptions of ongoing projects, and ways to participate
- **Basic shared art supplies**, such as sketching materials, paper, and craft tools to invite drop-in creativity

Organizers should work directly with participating artists in advance to determine what additional materials, tools, or display needs they may have. Many artists will bring their own supplies, but offering a baseline of shared materials can encourage wider attendee participation and spontaneous creativity.

When possible, the Artist's Corner should be co-located with the Silent Art Auction. This proximity helps draw traffic and reinforces the role of creativity in collections work. The space should remain inviting and accessible—somewhere attendees feel comfortable sitting, chatting, observing, or creating.

Artist Sales and Exhibiting Work

While the primary purpose of the Artist's Corner is educational, interactive, and community-building, offering artists the opportunity to sell their work can also serve as a meaningful way to thank them for volunteering their time and sharing their creative practice. Organizers should consult early with both the LOC and SPNHC leadership to determine what, if any, sales activity is permitted under conference policies and local legal regulations.

In most cases, vendors participating in the Exhibition Hall are required to register and pay a vendor fee. However, STEAMed SPNHC organizers may wish to advocate for more flexible policies for Artist's Corner participants, particularly local or invited artists contributing to programming. If permitted, these artists should be made fully responsible for handling their own payments, sales tax obligations, and logistics—no money should be exchanged through SPNHC or the organizing team.

Unconference

Planning Timeline

Planning the STEAMed SPNHC Unconference requires less intensive logistics than other programming elements but still benefits from early coordination and thoughtful facilitation. Once it's confirmed with the LOC, organizers can focus on outreach, session design, and light material preparation. Planning typically moves through three phases: **early confirmation and format development, continued promotion and logistics coordination, and final preparation and facilitation during the conference week.**

Early Planning (3–5 months out)

Organizers should confirm with the LOC that the Unconference is included in the official conference schedule and listed in relevant materials (see [Getting Started](#)). It's also helpful to incorporate the Unconference into early STEAMed SPNHC outreach, so attendees are aware of the opportunity and can begin thinking about how they might participate (see [Advertising and Outreach](#)). During this phase, organizers should decide whether they will facilitate the session themselves or recruit additional facilitators or co-hosts (see [Moderation and Facilitation](#)). It's also a good time to determine the general length of the session and begin drafting a rough session format and timing (see [Session Format](#)).

Mid-Stage Coordination (2–3 months out)

At this stage, organizers should continue generally advertising the Unconference. Organizers can also begin coordinating logistics with the LOC, confirming space and materials (see [Space and Setup](#)). If facilitators are being brought in, this is also a good time to touch base and begin outlining session flow and discussion prompts.

Final Preparations and Conference Week (1 month out – onsite)

As the conference nears, organizers should reconfirm logistics with the LOC. Begin gathering session materials (see [Space and Setup](#)). If planning to use an introductory slide or printed prompts, finalize and print these materials in advance. Prepare any icebreaker activity or suggested discussion topics to help spark conversation (see [Prompting Participation](#)). During the session, ensure that each group's insights are captured—whether through sticky notes, whiteboard photos, or informal note-taking. After the conference, compile a short summary of major themes or takeaways to share publicly or archive for future sessions.

Space and Setup

Organizers should work with the LOC to secure a space that allows for:

- **Moveable seating or breakout tables** to accommodate multiple discussion clusters
- **Open space** for posting topic pitches (e.g., whiteboards or wall space for sticky notes)
- **AV capabilities** including a projector or screen for opening slides and a microphone if the room is large or acoustically challenging

Because participants will move between phases of activity, it's helpful to keep the room uncluttered and adaptable.

In addition to space considerations, the following **materials should be on hand** to support the session:

- Sticky notes and pens (for topic pitching)
- Flip charts or large whiteboards with markers (for breakout group notes)
- Optional: pre-made prompt cards, example questions, or a presentation to inspire discussion

Session Format

The recommended unconference structure follows four main phases, which can be adapted based on session length and attendance:

1. **Welcome and Overview**

Briefly walk participants through the session structure and objectives. Provide a printed or projected slide overview and establish expectations for participation, note-taking, and respectful discussion. To help set the tone and encourage engagement, consider starting with an introductory presentation and a brief, active icebreaker activity.

2. **Topic Pitches**

Invite attendees to propose discussion topics. Participants can write their ideas on sticky notes or a whiteboard and present them briefly to the room. A facilitator can help consolidate similar ideas into a manageable number of themes.

3. **Breakout Groups**

Attendees self-select into small groups (3–8 people) based on shared interest in the pitched topics. Groups can meet at tables or distinct areas of the room. Provide optional prompts to help guide discussion.

4. **Report-Out and Wrap-Up**

Groups reconvene and share their key takeaways, either verbally or using shared materials (whiteboards, slides, collaborative docs). Facilitators may record these insights for later dissemination. Close the session with brief next steps and invitations to stay connected.

Prompting Participation

Because the Unconference relies on participant-driven discussion, it can be helpful to come prepared with example topics or prompts to help spark ideas—especially during the topic-pitching phase.

Suggested Discussion Topics

- Share ways Art has impacted you (as a starting topic)
- What brings you to this unconference?
- How can creative practices support scientific communication?
- Examples of successful collaborations between scientists and artists
- Using visual storytelling to increase access and engagement in collections
- Ethical considerations when interpreting and communicating collections through art
- Art as a tool for community outreach and DEI work in museums
- What does “sustainability” look like in collections when viewed through an artistic lens?
- Challenges of integrating art into institutional structures and workflows
- Building institutional support for interdisciplinary projects
- How can artists help reshape narratives? take on complex or controversial topics? start conversations?

These examples aren’t prescriptive, but can serve to model the kind of interdisciplinary and idea-focused conversations the Unconference is designed to support. In essence, this Unconference model is designed to facilitate finding others who are interested in the same topics as someone else, or bringing topics to light that then might intrigue and engage others. The nuance is that then individuals “pitch” their topic to see who else is interested.

Suggested Icebreakers

Including a brief, low-pressure icebreaker at the start helps participants loosen up, start conversations, and begin thinking about ideas they might want to explore or pitch. Possibilities include:

- **“Name tag sketch”** – ask participants to draw a simple doodle representing their role in collections, art, or science on a blank badge or sticky note.
- **“Common ground”** – in rotating pairs or trios, participants share how they currently use or engage with art—personally or professionally.
 - E.g. We started with, in groups of 2, introduce yourself and share one example of how art (or some piece / form of art) has affected / impacted you. (Does NOT have to be “SciArt” related).

Moderation and Facilitation

Facilitators play a crucial role in keeping the Unconference welcoming, productive, and participant-driven. At least one lead facilitator should guide the overall session, with additional volunteers or co-facilitators supporting breakout groups as needed. At least until

“Unconferences” are well known in our community, the facilitator will have to explain briefly what an unconference is, to start with. The facilitator’s primary job is to help keep discussions on track while ensuring that all voices have space to be heard. They should model inclusive behaviors—such as inviting quieter participants to share, redirecting dominating speakers, and maintaining focus on the group’s shared interests.

During the breakout period, facilitators can circulate between groups to offer gentle guidance, answer questions, and check that each group is capturing their key ideas (via sticky notes, shared docs, or poster paper). After reconvening, the facilitator should help each group present their insights succinctly, drawing connections between common themes.

General Logistics

Recruiting and Managing Volunteers

Volunteer recruitment should begin early through calls posted on SPNHC Slack, NHCOLL-L, and other outreach channels (see [Advertising and Outreach](#)). While a Volunteer Sign-Up Form is recommended for future events to streamline communication and capture availability, many people will also email the organizers directly or reach out informally. It’s important to track all inquiries and expressions of interest, including emails, verbal offers, Slack messages, and hallway conversations. Keeping a centralized tracking sheet helps ensure no potential volunteer or donor slips through the cracks. It also serves as a useful reminder to circle back to people later, whether to confirm help, finalize a donation, or follow up on a one-off offer that could easily be forgotten in the busy lead-up to the event.

[An Expressions of Interest template can be accessed here:](#)

[Expressions of Interest Template](#)

Use a Volunteer Calendar to organize shifts around high-traffic periods—such as setup, lunch breaks, poster sessions, and pickup day. While the auction space remains open for browsing throughout the week, volunteers are primarily needed during these busy times to help staff the auction table, answer questions, monitor bids, and assist with the Artist’s Corner, where they may help set up materials, support live art activities, or encourage attendee engagement.

[A template volunteer calendar can be accessed here:](#)

[Volunteer Calendar Template](#)

Be mindful of volunteers’ personal schedules, including conference sessions they may wish to attend or presentations they are giving. Assign shifts flexibly and check in with volunteers in advance to confirm their commitments.

In the weeks leading up to the conference, send a group email to all confirmed volunteers. Include the auction tracking sheet, volunteer calendar, conference schedule, and any other

relevant info. Ask volunteers to share their phone numbers and consider **creating a text or WhatsApp thread** for week-of logistics, last-minute updates, and shift coverage coordination.

Finally, plan to hold a brief in-person orientation with all available volunteers during the setup period. A 15–20 minute group meeting is usually sufficient to walk through responsibilities, auction procedures, key contacts, and the location of supplies.

Advertising and Outreach

General Outreach

Outreach for STEAMed SPNHC should be coordinated with the larger conference communications plan whenever possible. Because the LOC oversees official platforms and attendee mailing lists, it's ideal to involve them to help circulate initial calls for volunteers and donations. However, if LOC support isn't available or practical, STEAMed SPNHC organizers can manage and distribute outreach independently using SPNHC channels and affiliated networks.

Initial outreach should focus on recruiting volunteers, establishing awareness of the STEAMed SPNHC programming, and introducing key components like the Silent Art Auction and Artist's Corner. **Later communications should emphasize donation requests**, though these can be combined if needed. As confirmed activities and auction items begin to take shape, they can be featured in outreach materials. Visuals provided by donors (with permission) are especially useful for previewing the auction and building excitement, and artist spotlights or scheduled demonstrations can be promoted once finalized.

Broad outreach can be shared across all relevant platforms, such as relevant Slack channels, list-servs, social media, institutional networks, and partner organizations. Try to match where the conference is generally being advertised. As the conference approaches, however, outreach should become more focused, targeting SPNHC members, registered attendees, and internal channels. This helps maintain relevance, avoids audience fatigue, and ensures that reminders and updates are reaching those most likely to participate.

Posting across SPNHC channels is encouraged, but platform norms should be followed:

- On **Slack**, using the `@channel` ping is effective for visibility, but should be used sparingly.
- For [Natural History Collections listserver, NHCOLL-L](#), only subscribers can post. Messages must be in **plain text**, as the list automatically strips out any formatting, attachments, or embedded images and links. All essential information should be included directly in the body of the message. To share visuals, you can use the images submitted through the donation form, as long as they are made **publicly viewable**. Upload these to a shared Google Drive folder and include a **shortened link** (e.g., via [bit.ly](#)) in the message.

Template calls for donations can be accessed here:

[Advertisement Templates](#)

Targeted Outreach

In addition to general outreach and member communications, it's worthwhile to develop messaging aimed at individuals or groups with greater financial capacity or institutional influence—such as **deans, department chairs, museum directors, or organizational partners**. These audiences may be positioned to contribute high-value items, encourage departmental participation, or make financial contributions through discretionary funds. In addition, this provides a targeted opportunity to increase the visibility of SPNHC and collections and connect the related experts across departments to strengthen advocacy and agency and opportunities for collaboration.

One effective strategy is to draft a tailored message and work with the LOC to distribute it through established academic or museum networks. Since the LOC typically has existing relationships with local partners, their involvement helps ensure the message reaches the right people with the appropriate context and endorsement.

This kind of targeted outreach reinforces the goals of the Silent Art Auction—particularly its role in supporting the **SPNHC Student Travel Fund**—and broadens the base of support for STEAMed SPNHC initiatives. A customizable email template for institutional outreach is included in the shared materials folder.

A template targeted outreach email can be accessed here:

[Targeted Outreach Email Template](#)

Past Events

2025 - Lawrence, Kansas, USA

Location: University of Kansas
Events Held: Silent Art Auction, Artist's Corner, Unconference
Website: <https://spnhc2025.ku.edu/steamed-spnhc>
Results:

- 3 volunteers, 2 organizers
- 88 items donated to the Silent Auction, 34 donors
- ~\$4,000 raised for the SPNHC Student Travel Fund
- ~10 Unconference attendees
- Artist's Corner Group Sketch

2026 - Cape Town, South Africa

This could be you!